

An Optimal Clustering and Routing Protocol For Cognitive Radio Sensor Networks

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Abstract—Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), the data transfer model consists of a base station (called as sink) and sensors(called as nodes). Cognitive radio sensor networks (CRSNs), which has the ability to sense the spectrum and determine the vacant bands. A base station is typically located on the boundary or beyond the network area used to sense/measure data. The benefit of CRSNs is to maximize network lifetime and increase throughput, energy conservation during this node life. This paper proposes a Low-Energy Adaptive Clustering Hierarchical Protocol (LEACH) and optimal Clustering and Routing in Sensor Networks (OCRSN) schemes. Simulated results shows that proposed protocol gives better performance than existing.

Keywords- WSN, CRSN, OCRSN, LEACH, protocol, sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive Radio (CR) is an enabling technology, which allows CR users to exploit the spectrum allocated to Primary Users (PUs) in an opportunistic manner due to the spectrum scarcity challenges. However, Quality of Service (QoS) is a challenge in CR networks. A few studies have considered QoS in CR networks. Most researchers have concentrated on the protection of PUs due to the high priority they have. Due to the highly dynamic nature of cognitive vehicular networks, several sporadic links induce a long delay in the network. The selection of a stable route is therefore one of the key design factors to improve overall network stability, thereby reducing the end-to-end delay.

Figure 1: Cognitive radio network

To fully empower sensor networks with cognitive Internet of Things (IoT) technology, efficient medium access control protocols that enable the coexistence of cognitive sensor networks with current wireless infrastructure are as essential as the cognitive power in data fusion and processing due to shared wireless spectrum. Cognitive radio (CR) is introduced to increase spectrum efficiency and support such an endeavor,

which thereby becomes a promising building block toward facilitating cognitive IoT.

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) exclusively operates over unlicensed bands. Today, significant increase in the applications that use these bands brings about the coexistence problem. Hence, WSN needs additional capabilities to combat the interference incurred by the other applications.

Promising solution is to use the Cognitive Radio (CR) technology to arm the sensor nodes with opportunistic spectrum access (OSA) capability. Towards this end, cognitive radio sensor network (CRSN) is a recently emerging paradigm that aims to utilize the unique features provided by CR concept to incorporate additional capabilities to WSN. A CRSN is a distributed network of wireless cognitive radio sensor nodes, which sense an event signal and collaboratively communicate their readings over dynamically available spectrum bands in a multi-hop manner ultimately to satisfy the application-specific requirements.

Figure 2: Heterogeneous network of Cognitive radio

Reduced power consumption via OSA not only extends battery-constrained life-time of sensor nodes, but also limits overall energy consumption by sensor network. Thus, natural gaseous emission and dissipated heat by sensor network can be significantly reduced with the help of OSA to lead green distributed sensing networks.

II. BACKGROUND

K. Moyaba et al., [1] it is consider the problem of scheduling available multiple channels to the CR users when they are free. For this reason, it is propose a Cross Layer Design (CLD) scheme which jointly considers Media Access Control (MAC) and Network Layer as one optimisation problem. Specifically, it is consider the joint dynamic spectrum allocation, scheduling, routing, and transmit power control. Our scheme aims at reducing end-to-end delay, latency, interferences, and maximizing the network throughput. The performance evaluation of our scheme was conducted using the Network Simulator 2 (NS2) and compared to other CRAHN cross layer protocols. The results show that our scheme outperforms other cross layer protocols.

H. Ghafoor et al., [2] Software-defined networking (SDN) is a novel approach that improves network intelligence. To this end, it is propose a novel SDN-based routing protocol for cognitive vehicular networks that finds a stable route between source and destination. As this is a cognitive routing protocol, spectrum sensing is therefore the primary task of this algorithm to improve network stability by keeping primary user activity safe. it is apply a belief propagation algorithm for channel selection. This is an SDN-based vehicular communications scheme where two nodes can only communicate when they have consensus about a common idle channel. The protocol has two phases: the registering phase and the route prediction phase. The SDN main controller (MC) is responsible for a global view of the network, whereas several local controllers (LCs) are responsible for localized global views of the network. This layering of controllers into two kinds (MC and LCs) improves the network performance in terms of end-to-end delay, high delivery ratio, and low overhead. it is prove this in our simulation results by comparing our proposed scheme with two existing schemes (one with, and another without, SDN).

P. Chen et al., [3] In this work, primary users (PUs) refer to devices in existing wireless infrastructure, and secondary users (SUs) refer to cognitive sensors. For interference control between PUs and SUs, SUs adopt dynamic spectrum access and power adjustment to ensure sufficient operation of PUs, which inevitably leads to increasing latency and poses new challenges on the reliability of IoT communications. To guarantee operations of primary systems while simultaneously optimizing system performance in CR ad hoc networks (CRAHNs), thiswork proposes interference-aware flooding schemes exploiting global timeout and vaccine recovery schemes to control the heavy buffer occupancy induced by packet replications. The information delivery dynamics of SUs under the proposed interference-aware recovery-assisted flooding schemes is analyzed via epidemic models and

stochastic geometry from a macroscopic view of the entire system.

R. Jha et al., [4] The proposed algorithm uses distance as well as energy of nodes as a parameter to find optimum paths using particle swarm optimization. Among these selected paths, only one optimum path is selected which reduces the energy requirement of the network. According to this work there would be improvement in other parameters also such as end to end delay as well as throughput.

H. M. A. Abdullah et al., [5] Spectrum propagation and a reliable end-to-end transportation mechanism over the CRAHN. To elucidate these problems two Spectrum Map Opportunistic Routing (SMOR) algorithms such as SMOR-1 and SMOR-2 are proposed for regular and large-scale CRAHNs with wireless fading channels. However satisfying the network bandwidth, delivery ratio and the analysis to deal with transmission delay over such opportunistic links becomes important aspect. In order the solve the case and meet above stated limitations Hybrid Firefly Simulated Annealing based Spectrum Opportunistic Routing Algorithm(HFSA-SORA) is projected to the concerning of the spectrum map from local and global spectrum sensing information.

H. Ghafoor et al., [6] With the long propagation delay of an acoustic signal in underwater communications systems, relay node selection is one of the key design factors, because it significantly improves end-to-end delay, thereby improving overall network performance. To this end, the authors propose orthogonal frequency division multiplexing-based spectrum-aware routing (OSAR), a scheme in which spectrum sensing is done by an energy detector, and each sensor node broadcasts its local sensing results to all one-hop nodes via an extended beacon message. Each sensor node then selects nodes that agree on an idle channel, consequentially forming a set of neighbouring nodes.

K. Priyanka et al., [7] Wireless spread spectrum is a standout amongst the most valuable assets. With the fast development of the quantity of remote gadgets, interchanges over the unlicensed range groups get to be extremely swarmed. Data dissemination in the wireless environment is usually characterized as the spreading of data to numerous goals through communicating. The principle target is to achieve the most extreme number of neighbors with each sent parcel. The main objective of thework is to find the best routing and resource allocation strategies in order to minimize the average end-to-end delay of multiple data connections in the cognitive radio based wireless mesh network. Wireless mesh nodes utilize the cognitive radio to share the spectrum with primary users. Depending on the primary user's activities, the spectrum resources available to the cognitive mesh nodes are varying in both space and time. In this joint design scheme can accommodate the traffic load, or achieve half the delay compared to the disjoint methods.

III PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Figure 3: Flow Chart

LEACH:-

- Abbreviated as Low-Energy Adaptive Clustering Protocol is a hierarchical clustering protocol used for reducing power consumption in CRSNs.
- In Leach, the clustering task is rotated randomly among nodes based on duration and residual energy.
- Direct communication is done between CH's and BS.

OCRSN:-

- Abbreviated as Optimal Clustering and Routing in Sensor Networks is a multi-hop and multi path protocol used for energy preservation of various nodes in WSN.
- Uses neighbour discovery algorithm and cluster head selection algorithm to detect and select CH's.
- These CH's aggregate the data from all the nodes in the cluster transmits it to the sink.

IV SIMULATION RESULT

Figure 4: Cluster Network of OCRSN for 200 Nodes

Figure 4 is showing node movement and cluster formation using OCRSN protocol. Total node is taking 200 for this simulation.

Figure 5: Cluster Network of LEACH for 200 Nodes

Figure 5 is showing node movement and cluster formation using LEACH protocol. Total node is taking 200 for this simulation.

Figure 6: Comparison of Alive nodes for 100 rounds for 200 nodes in LEACH and OCRSN

Figure 9: Comparison of Average Energies of LEACH and OCRSN Protocol

Figure 7: Comparison of dead nodes for 100 rounds for 200 nodes in LEACH and OCRSN

Figure 10: Comparison of Packet Sent To Cluster Head

Figure 8: Comparison of Cluster Heads for 100 rounds for 200 nodes between LEACH and OCRSN

Table 1: Simulation Parameter

Sr. No	Parameters	Value
1	Total number of alive nodes	200
2	Total iterations preformed	100
3	Total dead node	79
4	Simulation time	6 sec
5	Cluster head	2%

Table 2: Comparison of proposed and previous work

Sr. No	Parameters	Previous Work	Proposed Work
1	Protocol	VDCOPR	LEACH, OCRSN
2	Network Topology	Bus	Hybrid
3	Energy drop	Sudden	Gradually
4	Simulation time	6 sec	12 Sec
5	Data transmission delay	5%	2%

V. CONCLUSION

Thus OCRSN increases the network lifetime in comparison with LEACH. It also improves the data transmission rate. OCRSN is best suitable for larger networks when compared to LEACH. LEACH and OCRSN are better protocol for cognitive radio sensing networks than the others existing sensor routing protocols. Simulated results show that the proposed protocols give better result than previous work.

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